

3beLiEVe: towards delivering the next generation of LMNO Li-ion battery cells and packs fit for electric vehicle applications of 2025 and beyond

Author, co-author (Do NOT enter this information. It will be pulled from participant tab in MyTechZone)

Affiliation (Do NOT enter this information. It will be pulled from participant tab in MyTechZone)

Abstract

This paper aims at providing the scientific community with an overview of the H2020 European project 3beLiEVe and of its early achievements. The project has the objective of delivering the next generation Lithium-Nickel-Manganese-Oxide (LNMO) battery cells, in line with the target performance of the “generation 3b” Li-ion battery technology, as per EU SET-plan Action 7. Its activities are organized in three main pillars: (i) developing the 3b next generation LMNO battery cell, equipped with (ii) an array of internal and external sensors and complemented by (iii) manufacturing and recycling processes at scale. At present, 3beLiEVe is approaching the completion of its first project year (out of a total project planned duration of 42 months). Hence this paper, beyond presenting the overall project’s structure and objectives, focuses on its earliest results in the fields of the cell material formulation, arrangement of sensors and design of the battery pack.

Introduction

3beLiEVe has its foundation in the concepts introduced by the EC White Paper “Roadmap to a Single European Transport Area”, published in March 2011, [1]. It is, in fact, ten years ago that the European Union clearly identified the three macro-objectives in the transport sector to be reached by 2050: decarbonization, digitalization, and implementation of seamless interaction between different transport modes. Focusing on the first objective, the quantitative target set for transport was reducing the greenhouse gas emissions by 60% by 2050 compared to 1990 levels; this was recognized as the necessary contribution from the transport area to achieve the overall global greenhouse gas emission reduction of 80-to-95% by 2050 compared to the 1990 baseline, first framed under the Kyoto protocol [2], and subsequently recalled under the Paris Agreement, [3]. This already ambitious target has been recently strengthened under the new Green Deal, where the Union has committed itself to achieve full carbon neutrality in all sectors of its economy, including transport, by 2050, [4].

Concerning decarbonization, electrification is the way to go in the automotive sector, and batteries are one of the key technologies necessary to enable the transition from conventional to hybrid and electric vehicles. Moreover, electrification of transport is not just an environmental challenge, but an economical one too. In fact, the conventional fuel vehicle industry accounts for 12 million jobs and 4% of the gross domestic product of the EU, being the largest private

investor in research and development in the Union [5]. This makes the automotive industry a formidable asset for the Union’s economy, although, at present, it is missing an industrial system in the field of battery cell production and manufacturing. This has created concerns in political and industrial circles that Europe may miss out on a key part of the electric vehicle value chain, lagging behind other regions of the world in a market where the European industry can realize significant profits.

To recover this gap, the European Commission launched in October 2017 the European Battery Alliance as a joint industry-led initiative to prevent a major technological dependence of the Union in battery cell supply. This initiative gave the impetus to launch in 2019 a € 250 million research programme labelled “LC-BAT”, [6]. It is under this framework that 3beLiEVe was conceived and funded, with the aim of delivering the generation 3b of LNMO cells and battery pack for the market of electrified vehicles of 2025 and beyond. On the same topic, 3 other projects were funded, forming the LC-BAT-5 cluster, [7].

3beLiEVe project structure, main technical objectives and end-user applications

The 3beLiEVe project [8] has the primary objective of delivering the next generation Lithium-Nickel-Manganese-Oxide (LNMO) cells, in line with the performance objectives of the “generation 3b” Li-ion battery cells, as per EU SET-plan Action 7, [9]. The project is executed by a consortium of 21 European partners from 10 different EU member states, receiving a contribution of approximately 10.8 million € over a project duration of 42 months, (i.e. from January 2019 to June 2023). The 3beLiEVe structure is built around three main technical pillars:

- the development of the next generation 3b material formulation, made of a LNMO cathode, combined with a high voltage electrolyte, and with a 10-20 wt.% Si-C anode;
- the engineering and delivery of an array of cell-internal and external sensors for monitoring all the relevant electric, thermal and mechanical cell parameters. These are used to govern the adaptive liquid cooling system of the battery pack managed by a smart battery management system with advanced diagnostic and operational functions;
- the development of a cradle-to-cradle approach to the 3b generation LMNO battery technology, encompassing the material selection, the cell and battery large-scale manufacturing processes, the battery 1st and 2nd life, and its dismantling and recycling phases.

The 3beLiEVe cell technology has the objective to achieve gravimetric and volumetric energy density values of 300 Wh/kg and 750 Wh/l, respectively, combined with the capability of 2,000+ deep cycles of which 10% at 3C+. Moreover, the 3beLiEVe cell aims to reach a production cost of approximately 140 €/kWh (calculated based on production at scale above 10 GWh/year by 2030), to be reduced to 90 €/kWh by factoring-in the residual value coming from the cells' second life application and the material recycling. Concerning end-user applications, the 3beLiEVe technology primarily aims at tackling the automotive sector, with applications ranging across the full spectrum of light and heavy-duty vehicles. Specifically, three categories of vehicles are targeted (and represented by OEMs within the consortium): (i) passenger plug-in hybrid and fully electric cars (from urban to premium segment, with variable battery capacities), (ii) plug-in hybrid electric buses (up to 19-tonnes / 12 meters) and (iii) medium duty fully electric city trucks (up to 27 tonnes).

3beLiEVe is, at present, reaching the completion of its first project year, thus many of the expected results mentioned above are yet to be delivered. Nonetheless, the project has already reached some key milestones, regarding the selection and testing of the active cell materials, the selection and arrangement of the sensors, and the design of the architecture of the battery pack. Hence, this paper focuses on presenting these results, providing the scientific community with an overview of its earliest achievements.

3beLiEVe active cell material formulation

The chemistry of the "generation 3b" is based on a positive electrode (i.e. "cathode") containing either a high-energy lithium nickel cobalt manganese oxide or a high-voltage spinel (and on a high-capacity silicon/carbon negative electrode (i.e. "anode"). Within the scope of 3beLiEVe project a selection of organic and water-based binders, conductive additives, an innovative electrolyte stable at high operating voltage, as well as graphite and Si-graphite based anode materials are evaluated. Here, we focus on the presentation of the LNMO high-voltage spinel as positive electrode material. The project has, in fact, selected the $\text{LiNi}_{0.5}\text{Mn}_{1.5}\text{O}_4$ (LNMO) spinel as one of the most promising candidates as positive electrode material for 3b-generation [9] lithium-ion batteries that can meet the high energy density demands set by the automotive sector (1,000 Wh/l by 2030 [10]), while avoiding environmentally and ethically burdened cobalt [11]. Its high energy density stems primarily from the elevated operating voltage of the $\text{Ni}^{2+/4+}$ redox couple at 4.7V vs. Li^+/Li . Additionally, $\text{Mn}^{3+/4+}$ redox couple at 4.1V vs. Li^+/Li can contribute to the total capacity increase. The presence of Mn^{3+} is linked to the deficiency of Ni and/or oxygen by charge neutrality. The role of Mn^{3+} in electrochemical cycling performance of LNMO is ambiguous. On the one hand, it can improve the conductivity and provide additional charge capacity at high cycling rates thanks to its comparatively lower redox potential [12]; on the other hand, it causes aging effects by dissolving and migrating to the anode as well as inducing lattice distortion through Jahn-Teller effect [13].

$\text{LiNi}_{0.5}\text{Mn}_{1.5}\text{O}_4$ crystallizes in a spinel structure, based on a *fcc* oxygen sublattice, in which Li^+ cations occupy tetrahedral sites and Ni^{2+} and $\text{Mn}^{3+/4+}$ cations occupy half of the octahedral sites. Two different distributions of the transition metal cations are reported for LNMO: in one case, Ni and Mn are randomly distributed over the octahedral sites (resulting in the so-called disordered *Fd3m* phase), while in the second case, Ni and Mn are distributed on these octahedral sites in an ordered fashion (ordered *P4332* phase), [14].

The disordered phase has been reported to have higher electrical conductivity, yielding a superior rate capability, [11, 15]. However, the crystallization of LNMO in the disordered phase is often linked to formation of Mn^{3+} , which can compromise the cycling stability, as above. The ubiquitous formation of rock-salt-type secondary phases during the synthesis process of LNMO is another intrinsic challenge of this material as it has detrimental effects on the charge transport properties, [16].

Besides, as a potential candidate for large-scale application, reducing the environmental impact of LNMO electrode production is essential. In this regard the transition from hazardous, teratogenic and expensive NMP to aqueous-based slurries offers the possibility to not only reduce environmental footprint but at the same time reduce processing cost. Thanks to a lower boiling point (100 °C vs 203 °C), the drying procedure can be sped up and the dispensability of recovering NMP solvent results in significant cost reduction [17].

Material properties

The 3beLiEVe consortium has selected three types of LNMO as potential candidates. At first these were subjected to thorough material analysis to gain insights on their physical properties. The materials were characterized using a wide range of techniques, including X-ray diffraction (XRD), Raman spectroscopy (RS), Nuclear Magnetic Resonance spectroscopy (NMR), Induced Coupled Plasma (ICP) and Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM). A brief summary of the principal material characteristics can be found in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of material properties of the three different LNMO candidates.

Property	Type #1	Type #2	Type #3	Technique
Phase	spinel, predominantly disordered (<i>Fd-3m</i>)	spinel, predominantly disordered (<i>Fd-3m</i>)	spinel, predominantly ordered (<i>P4₃32</i>)	(S)XRD, RS, NMR, NPD, TEM
Impurities	LiNiO	LiNiO	below detection limit	(S)XRD, NMR, NPD
Crystal size	165 nm	310 nm	294 nm	XRD
Morphology	Spherical particles, homogeneous, ϕ 10 μm	particles 3 μm , strong agglomeration	Spherical particles, homogeneous, ϕ 8 μm	SEM, Particle sizer
Stoichiometry	Ni/Li: 0,47(1), Mn/Li: 1,53(2)	Ni/Li: 0,47(1), Mn/Li: 1,57(3)	Ni/Li: 0,41(1); Mn/Li: 1,59(3)	ICP

As shown by the RS and reported in Table 1, type 1 and type 2 LNMO crystallize in the spinel phase in which the transition metals randomly occupy the 16*d* sites, while in type 3 Mn and Ni predominantly occupy specific sites 12*d* and 4*a*, respectively [18]. XRD and NPD affirmed that all three materials are highly pure and only negligible traces of rock salt phase were found in type 1 and 2, which are inherently linked to the processing of disordered LNMO [11]. In terms of morphology, type 2 differs strongly from type 1 and type 3, which have spherical polycrystalline particles with an average diameter of 10 μm , depicted in Figure 1.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 1. SEM micrographs of LNMO pristine materials, from (a) to (c).

Electrochemical performance vs Li for NMP based slurries

To test the electrochemical properties of the selected LNMO candidates, laminates were cast with an NMP-based slurry with a 84:8:8 formulation, following supplier's recipe [19]. Electrochemical half cells were cycled in coin cell (CC) configuration with LP30 electrolyte following a cycling protocol consisting of 3 formation cycles, 15 cycles of rate capability test at progressively increasing discharge rate from C/5 to 3C, followed by long-term cycling at 1C for 100 cycles with a slow cycle of C/5 every 20 cycles. The electrochemical signature of the three materials during the first cycle at C/20 is depicted in Figure 2. As expected, the signatures of disordered LNMO type 1 and 2 are very similar. They both exhibit a first plateau centered around 4V attributed to oxidation of Mn^{3+} followed by a second more pronounced plateau centered around 4.7 V. The latter can be divided into two sub-plateaus that are linked to the subsequent oxidation of Ni^{2+} to $3+$ and $4+$. The electrochemical cycling curve of the ordered LNMO type 3 differs significantly from that of the disordered type 1 and 2. Here, one can identify also the contribution of Mn^{3+} ; at 4V the plateau's extension is much smaller. Furthermore, the redox plateau of $Ni^{2+/4+}$ is upshifted by approximately 0.05V vs. Li^+/Li and the distinction between sub-plateaus is less salient than for the disordered phase, well in line with previously reported studies [15]. This upshift in redox reaction potential requires a raise of the upper voltage cut-off beyond 4.8V to ensure full de-lithiation of the ordered LNMO phase.

Figure 2. Electrochemical signature of LNMO candidates during first electrochemical cycle at C/20.

Initial reversible discharge capacities of 129-135 mAh/g were obtained with a coulombic efficiency (CE) of approximately 89%. For the subsequent formation cycle at C/10 an increase of coulombic efficiency to approximately 98% along with an increase in reversible capacity is observed for all three candidates. Upon progressive increase of the discharge rate to 3C, a decrease of reversible capacities is observed for type 1 and type 3, reaching approximately 123 mAh/g see Figure 3. Almost no capacity loss is observed for type 2 upon the six-fold increase of discharge rate from C/2 to 3C, reflecting excellent rate capability. These findings suggest that the property governing the rate capability of these LNMO candidates is the particle morphology rather than degree of TM metal ordering, as previously reported [11]. No loss of capacity was detected for LNMO type 1 and 3 during the subsequent 100 cycles at

1C, reflecting high cycling stability. For type 2, only a minor capacity fade of < 1% was recorded. The periodic oscillations of the capacity performance of LNMO type 3 reflects its sensitivity to slight temperature changes. The average cycling performance are summarized in Table 2.

Figure 3. Discharge capacities (solid markers) and coulombic efficiency (hollow crossed markers) of three LNMO candidates during formation, rate capability and capacity retention test.

Encouraged by these results, long term cycling measurements were conducted to monitor the capacity fade over hundreds of cycles. The discharge capacities of the three candidates for 650 cycles are depicted in Figure 4. It is salient that all three materials deliver very good capacity retention. No capacity fade is observed for LNMO types 1 and 3, while for LNMO type 2 a remarkable capacity retention of approx. 98% was maintained after over 600 cycles. Despite the higher capacity fade for LNMO type 2, absolute capacity values after 650 cycles are still higher than those for LNMO type 1 and 2. The fact that ordered and disordered LNMO phase 1 and 3 show equally stable electrochemical cycling is in contradiction to previous studies reporting superior capacity retention for the disordered phase [15, 20].

Table 2. Electrochemical performance of LNMO half cells vs Li.

Property	Type 1	Type 2	Type 3	Technique
Discharge capacity at C/10 (CE)	130 mAh/g (98,3%)	138 mAh/g (99,2%)	131 mAh/g (98,4%)	galvanostatic cycling, half-cell, CC, vs Li ⁺ /Li, LP30
Discharge rate capacity at 3C	123 mAh/g	132 mAh/g	123 mAh/g	
Capacity and retention after 100 cycles at 1C	127 mAh/g (100,5%)	133 mAh/g (99,5%)	126 mAh/g (101,5%)	

Figure 4. Capacity retention test of the three LNMO candidates in half cells at 1C with verification cycle every 20 cycles at C/5.

Electrochemical performance vs Li for aqueous based slurries

Water-based laminates were prepared with 90% active material and equal share of carbon additive and latex binder. Electrochemical testing was carried out analogous to NMP based laminates. The discharge performance of LNMO type 2 in aqueous and NMP-based slurry with similar areal loading are compared in Figure 5, revealing that not only similar overall capacities can be obtained but more importantly that equally stable cycling performance is obtained. The somewhat higher rate capability of NMP-based formulation can most likely be attributed to the higher content of active material, which results in reduced content of conductive additive (8 vs. 5 %). These are encouraging results on the path to more environmentally sustainable and cheaper processing of electrode films.

Figure 5. Electrochemical performance of NMP vs aqueous processed LNMO type 2 electrode.

Electrochemical performance in full cell assembly

First full-cell tests using LNMO type 1 laminate and two different loadings of graphite electrode (1.2 and 2.4 mAh/cm²) using LP30

electrolyte are presented in Figure 6. Satisfactory cycling cells with initial specific gravimetric capacity of approximately 110mAh/g were obtained, referring to the mass of active material. However, continuous but steady capacity fade is observed upon cycling, resulting in capacity loss of 18% and 35% after 200 cycles for 1.2 and 2.4mAh/cm² graphite electrode, respectively. The pronounced capacity fading of LNMO cathodes when coupled with graphite as negative electrode are well documented in the literature and its origin attributed to the transition metal migration and electrolyte degradation, [11, 21]. The scope of 3beLiEVe will be to investigate the electrode cross-talk, applying a wide range of characterization techniques while at the same time proposing solutions to mitigate these effects by active electrode material tailoring and application of novel high-voltage stable electrolyte formulations.

Figure 6. Electrochemical performance of LNMO type 1 in full cell configuration using two different loadings of graphite electrode (1.2 and 2.4mAh/cm²) and LP30 electrolyte.

3beLiEVe battery pack sensor array and architecture design

3beLiEVe aims at demonstrating the generation 3b LMNO battery cells in two battery packs, fit for both 400 and 800 V electric vehicle architectures. These packs need to be designed around three main constraints:

- the two packs need to reach one-fourth of the targeted nominal voltage (i.e. pack #1 is expected to reach 100 V and while pack #2 is expected to reach 200 V). This allows for four packs to be arranged in series to reach the final desired voltage, while variable capacities can be reached by parallelizing the packs, depending on the applications;
- both packs need to share the same module design, a key element to drive down the manufacturing costs;
- each module has a dedicated “sensors package” that matches the serial/parallel arrangement of the cells. The sensor package is designed maximizing redundancy and diversification principles.

Focusing on the latter, redundancy and diversification are key in this context. Specifically, redundancy means that the same physical variable is measured using multiple sensors, while diversification means that the two sensors use different methods or technologies to

measure the same quantity. The combination of these two features is crucial to validate measurements in the context of this research project and to minimize the probability of system failures. Hence the sensor package is designed around three independent sensor technologies that perform partially overlapping measurements at single cell level. A pouch cell format of 30 Ah capacity has been selected for 3beLiEVe. This choice is made based on the following elements:

- the 30 Ah pouch cell is in line with the requirements of the end-user applications (i.e. passenger plug-in hybrid and fully electric cars, plug-in hybrid electric buses and medium duty fully electric city trucks, as presented above), both as format as well as in terms of expected balance between energy and power density performance;
- the 30 Ah pouch cell lends itself well to experimental sensor integration work and is in line with the manufacturing capabilities across all stages of scaling in the project consortium.

The next sections will provide an overview of the adopted BMS and sensors, together with the considerations that determined the module and pack design. These were mainly accounting for the electrical and communications aspects of the module and pack architecture, while the mechanical integration is treated separately, and it is not a subject of this paper.

Overview of the BMS architecture

The 3beLiEVe project has adopted the foxBMS as primary BMS architecture, [22].

Figure 7. foxBMS architecture. foxBMS Slave: the battery module (including the sensor package). Bender insulation monitor: battery current dispersion monitor (safety devices). foxBMS Master: the central controller for battery management.

This is composed of one master complemented by several slave modules. The foxBMS master consists of a central controller that receives all the raw data produced by the physical sensors. These data are used to compute the SoX parameters and determine control actions like active cooling and charge balancing. The master communicates with the slaves, consisting of circuit boards that include all the electronic components of the sensor package located in each module. Inside a slave node, all the sensors communicate locally (at module level) using an isolated I2C bus. All the slave modules send and receive data using a proprietary isolated bus. A schematic of the foxBMS is depicted in Figure 7.

Internal and external sensors

3beLiEVe takes advantage of existing internal and external sensor technologies at different levels of maturity, selected among those under development by the project's participating organizations. The selected types of sensors are: (i) the MC 33775A chip (external), (ii) an internal opto-electronic sensor and (iii) the Sensiplus chip (external).

The MC 33775A is a single-chip solution under development by NXP [22], capable of measuring the individual voltage of a string of cell in series (from a minimum of four to a maximum of fourteen cells). The current measurement is performed at string level by a sensor directly connected with the foxBMS master. The chip is also capable of measuring up to eight temperature points and of handling a local I2C bus as master node. The I2C bus is used to communicate with the other sensors at module level and the chip also handles (under the control of the BMS master) the passive charge balancing functions at cell level. The chip can communicate with the foxBMS master via a proprietary pulse transformer isolated bus. The chip has two bus ports that enable a daisy-chain communication bus over multiple battery modules, and it includes an internal power supply connected with the cell string at module level.

The internal opto-electronic sensor is a technology under development by Insplorion, [24] and it is able to measure the ion concentration inside the electrolytic cell, [25, 26]. The physical sensor is an optical fiber with an active end realized with a thin metallic (usually gold) substrate. When the thickness of the substrate is comparable with the wavelength of the incident radiation (typically in the infrared range) the metallic substrate behaves like a plasma and the electromagnetic radiation may interact with the substances deposited over the substrate. This physical effect is called surface plasmonic resonance. Therefore, by measuring the electromagnetic properties of the metallic substrate, it is possible to derive information about the chemical composition of the substances in contact with the substrate. This sensor is designed to be sensible to the Li-ion concentration, from which one can compute the State of Charge (SoC) and State of Health (SoH) of the individual cell. Moreover, this sensor can use the I2C bus of the MC 33775A chip and can be powered by the chip itself. Being an internal sensor, each cell needs at least one such opto-electronic sensor for determining SoC and SoH.

Finally, the Sensiplus is a very low-power device capable of implementing on-line (i.e. without disconnecting the cell), real-time measurements of the internal impedance of the individual cell by using lock-in technique, under development by Sensichips, [27]. The electrical impedance spectroscopy measurements allow estimation of the SoC and SoH of the cell, thus providing a second measurement to that of the internal opto-electronic sensors. Moreover, Sensiplus includes an internal, programmable current source with a direct current measurement and a synchronous detector (lock-in amplifier) capable of measuring the in-phase (real component) and in-quadrature (imaginary component) of the AC voltage across the cell induced by the injected current. Sensiplus can also measure the DC voltage of the cell, temperatures (using external RTD or NTC sensors) and mechanical stresses (using a strain gauge glued on the external body of the cell). The voltage and temperature measurements can double those from the MC 33775A chip, while mechanical measurements are useful to estimate the pouch cell expansion and contraction as a function of the SoC (charged cells tend to swell). Moreover, overstressed cells exhibit anomalous deformation on the external body, therefore the mechanical stress measurements can be

used to diagnose the safety-critical cells. Sensiplus is powered by the cell itself and can monitor either single cells or pairs of cells in parallel.

Battery module architecture design

Considering the sensor array above, one can see that all the relevant electrical measurements at cells are at least doubled and measured by a minimum of two different, independent sensors, thus achieving a satisfactory level of redundancy and diversification. Moreover, looking at the functional constraints of the sensors, the MC 33775A chip constitutes the "bottleneck" to determine the minimum number of cells per module, since it is the only one that needs a minimum number of four cells to operate.

Based on this consideration, two preliminary candidate arrangements for the module have been considered, each consisting of 8 cells per module. These are the $2 \times 4S-1P$ (Figure 8, candidate #1) and $4S-2P$ (Figure 9, candidate #2). Looking at these two diagrams, the $2 \times 4S-1P$ module needs 18 sensors (i.e. $2 \times$ MC 33775A chips, $8 \times$ opto-electronic sensors, and $8 \times$ Sensiplus), while the $4S-2P$ architecture needs just 13 sensors (i.e. $1 \times$ MC 33775A chips, $8 \times$ opto-electronic sensors, and $4 \times$ Sensiplus). Hence, from a cost perspective the latter is favorable. On the other hand, dissimilarities in cell properties are the inevitable result of manufacturing tolerances, as well as usage conditions resulting in different parameters such as inner resistance, polarization time constraints, and capacity [27].

Figure 8. $2 \times 4S-1P$ module design (candidate #1). C1-C8: cells inside the module; SP-EIS: Sensiplus Electrical Impedance measurement; ISO: I2C isolator for SP-ISO; TS: temperature sensor; I2C: local I2C bus; FO-Cx Insplorion fiber optic sensor; NXP: voltage and temperature cell measurements plus cell balancing; TPL: transformer-isolated bus between modules and foxBMS Master unit.

Figure 9. 4S-2P module design (candidate #2). C1-C8: cells inside the module; SP-EIS: Sensiplus Electrical Impedance measurement; ISO: I2C isolator for SP-ISO; TS: temperature sensor; I2C: local I2C bus; FO-Cx Insplorion fiber optic sensor; NXP: voltage and temperature cell measurements plus cell balancing; TPL: transformer-isolated bus between modules and foxBMS Master unit.

In this regard, the topology connection of battery cells plays a prominent role in the battery pack design, since the different SoC, SoH, and voltages can limit the power and energy capabilities of the complete battery pack [28]. Moreover, the accuracy of SoC estimation if cell-to-cell variations are considered also plays an important role in the design. In other words, it is important to know how the electrical configuration of the cells can affect the electric and degradation mechanism of a battery pack. This can lead to a better battery cell configuration for different applications in the early design stage, regardless of sensor packaging.

Figure 10. The physical orientation of 2P2S.

Although the literature has arrived at different conclusions [28–30], the effect of these variations on the performance and aging mechanism has been pointed out in different stages. In ref. [29], an 8s14p cell interconnection topology was built, then the capacity matching was performed before spot welding. It is concluded that

regardless of resistance, variations and inhomogeneous temperature distributions, the difference in capacity inhomogeneity is lower than 1%. However, the used cells in ref. [29] are high-quality lithium-ion battery cells and the result is limited to 1,200 Full Equivalent Cycles (FECs). Moreover, it is not mentioned in the previous work how mismatches in internal resistance in parallel cell connections is handled at the end of the discharge cycle leading.

This leads to premature aging and is addressed in ref. [28], stating that the impact of resistance mismatch on aging is substantially more important than any effect of single-cell resistance. Furthermore, in ref. [30], the imbalanced currents in parallel connection with 60 Ah LiFePO₄ battery cells are analyzed. The result shows that continuously increasing imbalanced currents are mainly responsible for the capacity fade in parallel connections.

To evaluate the impact of dissimilarities in cell properties in a parallel configuration, a physical orientation of pack model consisting of 4 cells (2S-2P) has been modelled in Simscape environment, shown in Figure 10. Two cells in parallel have different internal resistances and OCV behaviors. In this case, two cells are in parallel, and cell no. 06 has double the internal resistance of cell no.14. A discharge current is then imposed on the module.

Figure 11. Current distribution and temperature behavior within two parallel-connected cells upon cycling.

When two cells with different internal resistance are discharged in parallel, each cell is under different current profiles as can be seen in Figure 11. Early in the discharging process, the cell with higher resistance experiences a lower current, and the less resistive cell sees a higher current. This results in the less resistive cell being fully discharged sooner than the cell with higher resistance. The difference in current is less at the early stage of discharge and increases later. At the end of the discharge process, balancing between the cells shows that the more resistive cell charges the less resistive cell as OCV and SoC of the cells are different. Note that the current distribution curve depends on OCV vs. SoC behavior, as the OCV curve depends on the li-ion cell chemistries such as LiFePO₄, which has a flat voltage curve, while a higher slope can be seen in the case of chemistries such as LiCoO₂, LiMn₂O₄ and so on. This difference in current could be harmful if cell and electrical protection devices are not implemented. This is especially relevant in the 3beLiEve project, which will develop cells with high energy density and voltage. Moreover, temperature behaviors show the less resistive cell (no. 14) has higher temperature evolution than cell no. 06 due to higher current flow. As high current rate and temperature are the two important stress factors for capacity degradation, it is expected that cell no. 06 will age sooner than other cells. The conclusion for parallel-connected cells is that mismatching internal resistance leads to a higher current and temperature evolution, resulting in an accelerated capacity fade.

Furthermore, since individual current measurement is not typically employed in a parallel configuration, the current variation between the two cells cannot be detected by the battery management system. Moreover, it has been shown that variation in current can change the SoC of the battery cell, which means the cells in parallel may not be at the same SoC even though they have the same terminal voltage. They may therefore degrade at different rates. Since accurate state estimation plays an important role in BMS, in the 3beLiEVe project we have opted to use a series-only electrical configuration of cells within the module in order to measure the voltage of individual cells. This allows us to protect and accurately estimate the state of each individual cell.

To sum up, two main drawbacks of parallel configuration would be as follows:

- the individual measurements at cell level are only performed by the internal fiber optic sensor. In fact, both external sensors (NXP and Sensiplus) perform measurements and cell balancing on the two cells in parallel. This reduces the overall number of measurement points, and thus their redundancy and differentiation;
- due to the inevitable differences in the manufacturing process and operating conditions, two cells in parallel would have different internal electrochemical parameters. These differences would create internal transient currents (between two cells in direct parallel) that accelerate the aging of both cells.

Based on these considerations, both candidates #1 and #2 have been discarded, and a third candidate has been considered, i.e. the 8S module (Figure 12). This solution is equipped with a lower number of sensors compared to the 2 × 4S-1P (i.e. 17 sensors, 1 × MC 33775A chips, 8 × opto-electronic sensors, and 8 × Sensiplus) and, at the same time, avoids the drawbacks of the 4S-2P described above. This topology has been finally selected for 3beLiEVe as the building block for the battery pack's architecture.

Battery pack architecture design

The battery pack demonstrator design in 3beLiEVe is based on the 8S module architecture, where the number of 8 cells per module has been selected based on the best compromise with the envisaged cooling system. This module structure allows for approximately 36 V of nominal voltage (assuming a cell nominal voltage of 4.5V), thus 3 modules in series are needed to achieve the 100 V in one demonstrator, while 6 modules are needed for the 200 V second demonstrator. Based on the target 30 Ah /135 Wh pouch cell format, each module has a capacity of approximately 1,080 Wh, which becomes equivalent to 3,240 Wh for the 100 V and 6,480 Wh for the 200V arrangement. Thus, the 3beLiEVe battery demonstrator at 100V will consist of 4 parallel legs of 3 modules each, for a total capacity of 12,960 Wh with 96 cells. Similarly, the 3beLiEVe battery demonstrator at 200V will consist of 2 parallel legs of 6 modules each, for the same capacity and cell count. These configurations are considered the most beneficial for the objectives of the project.

Conclusions

This paper presents the structure and objectives of the 3beLiEVe project, with an in-focus look at the results achieved at the end of its first execution year (out of a total project duration of 42 months). These refer mainly to two areas: (i) the active material cell formulation, and (ii) the sensor selection, arrangement and preliminary design of the battery pack.

Concerning the active material cell formulation, three candidates for the LMNO cathode have been subjected to material analysis. Their electrochemical properties vs Li for NMP and aqueous based slurries have been investigated in half coin cells. These investigations focused on determining the discharge capacity, the coulombic efficiency and the capacity retention of the three types of LMNO, identifying the potential candidate to step up to full cell tests.

Concerning the preliminary design of the battery pack, the different requirements of the internal and external sensors have been analyzed, and virtually implemented in various battery module designs,

Figure 12. 8S module design (candidate #3) – 3beLiEVe module. C1-C8: cells inside the module; SP-EIS: Sensiplus Electrical Impedance measurement; ISO: I2C isolator for SP-ISO; TS: temperature sensor; I2C: local I2C bus; FO-Cx Insplosion fiber optic sensor; NXP: voltage and temperature cell measurements plus cell balancing; TPL: transformer-isolated bus between modules and foxBMS Master unit.

presenting the technical considerations that have led to the selection of the 8S module architecture equipped with 17 sensors as the most appropriate for the 3beLiEVe objectives. This leads to the two battery architectures of the project, consisting of 4 parallel legs of 3 modules each for the 100 V type and of 2 parallel legs of 6 modules each for the 200 V type.

Despite the initial nature of the presented results, this paper provides the interim achievements of a large-scale research European project, with the aim of delivering the next generation of LMNO Li-ion battery cells and packs. These constitute the basis for moving forward with the with project's tasks and delivering its overall objectives.

Acknowledgments

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Contact Information

Dr. Michele De Gennaro, e-mail: michele.degennaro@ait.ac.at;

References

1. European Commission, "Roadmap to a Single European Transport Area", <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:52011DC0144>, accessed Oct. 2020.
2. European Environment Agency (EEA), "Kyoto burden-sharing targets for EU-15 countries", 2005.
3. European Commission, "Climate Action: Reducing emissions from transport", http://ec.europa.eu/clima/policies/transport/index_en.htm, accessed Oct. 2020.
4. European Commission, https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/european-green-deal-communication_en.pdf, accessed Oct. 2020.
5. European Commission, https://ec.europa.eu/growth/sectors/automotive_en, accessed Oct. 2020.
6. European Commission, https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2018-2020/main/h2020-wp1820-cc-activities_en.pdf, accessed Oct. 2020.
7. 3beLiEVe website, "LC-BAT-5 Cluster", <https://www.3believe.eu/lc-bat-5-cluster/>, accessed Dec. 2020.
8. 3beLiEVe website, www.3believe.eu, accessed Oct. 2020.
9. European Commission, "Strategic Energy Technology and Information System (SETIS), Batteries - Implementation", 2017.
10. EUCAR, "Battery requirements for future automotive applications," 2019.
11. Manthiram A., Chemelewski K., and Lee E.-S., "A perspective on the high-voltage LiMn_{1.5}Ni_{0.5}O₄ spinel cathode for lithium-ion batteries", *Energy Environ. Sci.*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 1339, 2014, [doi:10.1039/c3ee42981d](https://doi.org/10.1039/c3ee42981d).
12. Axmann P., Gabrielli G., and Wohlfahrt-Mehrens M., "Tailoring high-voltage and high-performance LiNi_{0.5}Mn_{1.5}O₄ cathode material for high energy lithium-ion batteries" *J. Power Sources*, vol. 301, pp. 151–159, Jan. 2016, [doi:10.1016/j.jpowsour.2015.10.010](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2015.10.010).
13. Yang J., Han X., Zhang X., Cheng F., and Chen J., "Spinel LiNi_{0.5}Mn_{1.5}O₄ cathode for rechargeable lithiumion batteries: Nano vs micro, ordered phase (P4332) vs disordered phase (Fd $\bar{3}m$)" *Nano Res.*, vol. 6, no. 9, pp. 679–687, Sep. 2013, [doi:10.1007/s12274-013-0343-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s12274-013-0343-5).
14. Cabana J. *et al.*, "Composition-Structure Relationships in the Li-Ion Battery Electrode Material LiNi_{0.5}Mn_{1.5}O₄" *Chem. Mater.*, vol. 24, no. 15, pp. 2952–2964, Aug. 2012, [doi:10.1021/cm301148d](https://doi.org/10.1021/cm301148d).
15. Wang L., Li H., Huang X., and Baudrin E., "A comparative study of Fd-3m and P4332 'LiNi_{0.5}Mn_{1.5}O₄'", *Solid State Ion.*, vol. 193, no. 1, pp. 32–38, Jun. 2011, [doi:10.1016/j.ssi.2011.04.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssi.2011.04.007).
16. Casas-Cabanas M., Kim C., Rodríguez-Carvajal J., and Cabana J., "Atomic defects during ordering transitions in LiNi_{0.5}Mn_{1.5}O₄ and their relationship with electrochemical properties", *J. Mater. Chem. A*, vol. 4, no. 21, pp. 8255–8262, 2016, [doi:10.1039/C6TA00424E](https://doi.org/10.1039/C6TA00424E).
17. Bresser D., Buchholz D., Moretti A., Varzi A., and Passerini S., "Alternative binders for sustainable electrochemical energy storage – the transition to aqueous electrode processing and bio-derived polymers," *Energy Environ. Sci.*, vol. 11, no. 11, pp. 3096–3127, 2018, [doi:10.1039/C8EE00640G](https://doi.org/10.1039/C8EE00640G).
18. Aktekin B. *et al.*, "Cation Ordering and Oxygen Release in LiNi_{0.5-x}Mn_{1.5+x}O_{4-y} (LNMO): In Situ Neutron Diffraction and Performance in Li Ion Full Cells," *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.*, vol. 2, no. 5, pp. 3323–3335, May 2019, [doi:10.1021/acsaeam.8b02217](https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaeam.8b02217).
19. Fink C., Fahl L., Weiland J., and Højberg J., "Characterization of high-voltage between Ni content in spinel, lattice size and 4V capacity", Batteries White Paper, <https://www.topsoe.com/hubfs/DOWNLOADS/DOWNLOADS%20-%20White%20papers/Characterization%20of%20high-voltage.pdf>, accessed Dec. 2020.
20. Xu X., Deng S., Wang H., Liu J., and Yan H., "Research Progress in Improving the Cycling Stability of High-Voltage LiNi_{0.5}Mn_{1.5}O₄ Cathode in Lithium-Ion Battery", *Nano-Micro Lett.*, vol. 9, no. 2, p. 22, Apr. 2017, [doi:10.1007/s40820-016-0123-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s40820-016-0123-3).
21. Pieczonka N. P. W. *et al.*, "Understanding transition-metal dissolution behavior in LiNi_{0.5}Mn_{1.5}O₄ high-voltage spinel for lithium ion batteries", *J. Phys. Chem. C*, vol. 117, no. 31, pp. 15947–15957, Aug. 2013, [doi:10.1021/jp405158m](https://doi.org/10.1021/jp405158m).
22. FoxBOM website, <https://foxbms.org/technical-specifications/>, accessed Oct. 2020
23. NXP website, <https://www.nxp.com/>, accessed Oct. 2020.
24. Insplorion website, <https://www.insplorion.com/en/>, accessed Oct. 2020.
25. Raghavan A. *et al.*, "Embedded fiber-optic sensing for accurate internal monitoring of cell state in advanced battery management systems part 1: Cell embedding method and performance", *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 341, pp. 466-473, 2017.
26. Zou C., Hu X., "Electrochemical Control of Lithium-Ion Battery Health-Aware Fast Charging", *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, 2017. [doi:10.1109/TIE.2017.2772154](https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2017.2772154).
27. Sensichip website, <https://www.sensichips.com/>, accessed Oct. 2020
28. Bruen T., Marco J., "Modelling and experimental evaluation of parallel connected lithium ion cells for an electric vehicle battery system", *Journal of Power Sources*, vol 310, pp. 91-101, 2016, [doi:10.1016/j.jpowsour.2016.01.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2016.01.001).
29. Gogoana R., Pinson M.B., Bazant M.Z., Sarma S.E., "Internal resistance matching for parallel-connected lithium-ion cells and impacts on battery pack cycle life", *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 252, pp. 8-13, 2014, [doi:10.1016/j.jpowsour.2013.11.101](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2013.11.101).

30. Campestrini C., Keil P., Schuster S.F., Jossen A., “Ageing of lithium-ion battery modules with dissipative balancing compared with single-cell ageing”, *Journal of Energy Storage* vol. 6, pp. 142-152, 2016, [doi:10.1016/j.est.2016.03.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2016.03.004).
31. Shi W., Hu X., Jin C., Jiang J., Zhang Y., Yip T., “Effects of imbalanced currents on large-format LiFePO4/graphite batteries systems connected in parallel”, *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 313, pp. 198-204, 2016, [doi:10.1016/j.jpowsour.2016.02.087](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2016.02.087).

Definitions/Abbreviations

AC/DC	Alternate / Direct Current
BMS	Battery Management System
CC	Coin cell
CE	Coulombic efficiency
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FEC	Full Equivalent Cycle
H2020	Horizon 2020 (European research programme)
I2C	Inter Integrated Circuit
ICP	Induced Coupled Plasma
LMNO	Lithium-Nickel-Manganese-Oxide
NMP	N-methylpyrrolidone
NMR	Nuclear Magnetic Resonance spectroscopy

NPD	Neutron Powder diffraction
NTC	Negative Temperature Coefficient (resistance, referred to a sensor)
OCV	Open Circuit Voltage
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
PVDF	Polyvinylidene fluoride
RS	Raman Spectroscopy
RTD	Resistance Temperature Dependent (referred to a sensor)
SoC	State of Charge
SoH	State of Health
SoX	State of (generic)
SET-plan	Strategic Energy Technology plan
Si-C	Silicon-Carbon (anode)
TEM	Transmission Electron Microscopy
TM	Transition metal
(S)XRD	(Synchrotron based) X-ray diffraction

Dear Reviewers, dear SAE WCX Organizers,

Please find hereunder **in red** the reply to each of the comments received on the SAE WCX 21PFL-0050.

Kind Regards,

Michele DE GENNARO (corresponding author)

Reviewer #: 271469

The reviewers want to thank the authors for presenting a complete description of the EU project 3beLiEVe.

The paper includes a summary of the research performed within the 3beLiEVe project, starting from the cell chemistry up to the battery pack design.

The paper is complete and well written.

Thanks for the positive feedback.

It could be interesting to add some examples of other EU projects related to batteries and their scope and outcome.

To address this comment, a sentence has been added at the end of the Introduction: “On the same topic, 3 other projects were funded, forming the LC-BAT-5 cluster, [7]”.

Then, the aspect of second life is discussed in the introduction, however, no additional information are provided in the battery pack design section.

Indeed, the aspect of second life is mentioned in the paragraph about the 3beLiEVe project structure. As mentioned, this is key to develop a comprehensive cradle-to-cradle approach to the 3b Generation, and it plays a key role in the project. No additional info is provided in the battery pack design section, since this mostly based on electrical and communications considerations, while the mechanical part is treated separately and it is, at the present, at a too early stage to be presented. To clarify this, a sentence has been added:

“These were mainly accounting for the electrical and communications aspects of the module and pack architecture, while the mechanical integration is treated separately, and it is not a subject of this paper.”.

Reviewer #: 271859

An interesting and relevant topic is presented. This paper reports the latest development in the H2020 European project 3beLiEVe. The paper discusses cell active materials, cell preliminary performance, model design, and pack design. The overall quality of the paper is high. The reviewer found the paper easy to understand.

Thanks for the positive feedback.

Please find the list of suggestions and comments below:

1. General: Please review [the SAE requirement for figures](#) and update figures and figure captions accordingly. Attention is needed for the location of the caption, the font color, and the location of the "period".

Done.

2. General: Please review [the SAE requirement for equations](#) and update equations accordingly. Please pay attention to the location of the equation and how the equation is expected to be mentioned in the text.

Done. No eq. in the paper.

3. General: Please review [the SAE requirement for tables](#) and update tables and table captions accordingly. Attention is needed for the location of the caption, the font color, and the location of the "period".

Done.

4. General: Please correct the formats of the headings. Please review this [example](#) provided by SAE.

Done.

5. General: Please make sure i.e. and e.g. are used properly. 'E.g.' stands for exempli gratia and means “for **example**.” 'I.e.' is the abbreviation for id est and means “in other words.”

Done.

6. Introduction, page 1: It is true that "...electrification is the way to go in the automotive sector, and batteries are one of the key technologies necessary to enable the transition from conventional to hybrid and electric vehicles." Please consider referring to the following reference to support the statement:

Zhu, Di, and Ewan Pritchard. *NCSU Year Three Final Technical Report*. No. 2014-01-2907. SAE Technical Paper, 2014.

The authors have revised the suggested reference, but it is unclear while this is relevant in view of justifying the sentence "electrification is the way to go...". The authors have decided to skip this reference.

7. Battery Pack Architecture Design, page 8: It is mentioned in the paper that "...the number of 8 cells per module has been selected based on the best compromise with the envisaged cooling system." Would consider the capability of the sensing chips make a difference? The sensing chip usually has a preferred cell configuration (e.g., 10 cells per chip).

The authors are not sure whether the reviewer is referring to the MC 33775A chip, to the Sensiplus chip, or to both, (they are all described in the section "Internal and external sensors"). Regardless on this uncertainty, the MC 33775A chip allows for flexible configurations (from a minimum of four to a maximum of fourteen cells), while the Sensiplus chip can either work single cells or pairs of cells in parallel. Hence the chosen configuration matches with the requirements of both chips, and these are not considered to further constrain / influence the selected architecture design.

Thus, the answer is no, they do not make a difference, beyond that already presented in the paper.

8. Battery Pack Architecture Design, page 8: It is written in the paper that "Based on the target 30 Ah /135 Wh pouch cell format, each module has a capacity of approximately 1,080 Wh, which becomes equivalent to 3,240 Wh for the 100 V and 6,480 Wh for the 200V arrangement." What is the most common Ah capacity in the current products? How was the 30 Ah target selected?

The 30 Ah has been selected based on the combination of two elements: (i) select a cell in line with the requirements of the end-user application, both in term of format as well as in terms of energy and power density performance, and (ii) select a cell in line with the automation production requirements of the 3beLiEVe partners. To clarify this, a sentence has been added:

"A pouch cell format of 30 Ah capacity has been selected for 3beLiEVe. This choice is made based on the following elements:

- the 30 Ah pouch cell is in line with the requirements of the end-user applications (i.e. passenger plug-in hybrid and fully electric cars, plug-in hybrid electric buses and medium duty fully electric city trucks, as presented above), both as format as well as in terms of expected balance between energy and power density performance;*
- the 30 Ah pouch cell lends itself well to experimental sensor integration work and is in line with the manufacturing capabilities across all stages of scaling in the project consortium."*

9. References, page 9: SAE uses different reference formats for different reference types. Please review [the SAE reference requirement](#) and update the references.

e.g., Ref. 27 is a journal that should be in the same format as Ref. 11.

The reference format has been adjusted.